

Mapping a Quantum Potential to a Delta Function and the Uncertainty Principle

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In (1), an approximate method of obtaining the ground state energy is presented by mapping a Schrodinger equation with a given potential $V(x)$ into one with delta function potential with an appropriate weight. Various examples are presented in both (1) and (2). It should be noted that although this approach yields the exact ground state energy for the oscillator it does not yield a correct answer for a particle in a box with infinite potentials at the wall. In this note, we try to investigate a possible physical argument for a mapping into a delta function and argue it is linked to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. We also suggest that the weighting used in (1) i.e. $U1 = \int_{x1,x2} V(x) dx$ where $(x1,x2)$ are classical turning points, should be multiplied by a constant b which ultimately cancels in the expression for the ground state energy.

Mapping a Schrodinger Equation $V(x)$ into a Delta Function: The Approach of (1)

In (1), a Schrodinger equation with $V(x)$ is mapped into one with a delta function potential. Two equations are used. First:

$$S = \int_{x1,x2} V(x) dx = E (x2-x1) \quad ((1)) \quad (\text{where } (x1,x2) \text{ are the classical turning points } V(x_i)=E.)$$

We argue that the LHS of ((1)) should be multiplied by a constant b to account for both the integrals of potential and kinetic energy within $x2-x1$.

Secondly:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} F(x) + S \delta(x-x_0) F(x) = E F(x) \quad ((2))$$

We again argue that S should be replaced with bS .

((2)) is the standard delta function problem with an energy solution of:

$$E = -1/2m \frac{d^2}{dx^2} S \quad ((3))$$

Combining ((1)) and ((3)) yields the ground state energy:

$$E_{\text{ground}} = -2/m \int_{x1,x2} \frac{1}{(x2-x1)(x2-x1)} \quad ((4))$$

Thus, b cancels. We later argue that ((4)) has the form of an uncertainty principle result.

Motivation for the Delta Function Mapping

In this note, we seek a motivation for the delta function potential mapping used in ((2)), especially given that the result ((4)), while being exact for an oscillator, is approximate for a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls.

We begin with ((1)) $bS = b \int_{x_1, x_2} V(x) dx = E (x_2 - x_1)$ where (x_1, x_2) are the classical turning points. We insert the factor b because there is both kinetic and potential energy within the interval (x_1, x_2) . In (1), no factor is used, but one may see that ((1)) is not satisfied for an oscillator without b .

Next, we argue that the range of x may be infinite, such as for an oscillator. In such a case, the interval $x_2 - x_1$ is tiny compared to the overall range, even though most of the energy is in this interval. As a result, we suggest that $bS / (x_2 - x_1)$ from ((1)) goes to infinity if $x_2 - x_1 \rightarrow 0$. Of course, $x_2 - x_1$ represents a fixed length. Different potentials $V(x)$ have different turning points and $V(x_i) = E$ and different lengths $x_2 - x_1$. Setting $x_2 - x_1$ to 0 at a point ignores the length of the interval, but this length is incorporated in S . One is really interested in W^*WE in the range dx where W is the wavefunction. If the wavefunction could be considered constant in the interval, which is the case for a delta function potential, then one has Sb which is $E(x_2 - x_1)$ in this range. The rest of the energy comes from outside the region.

This then leads to the idea of ((2)) i.e. a delta function potential:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} F + bS \delta(x-x_0) F = E_{\text{ground}} F \quad ((5))$$

where $F(x)$ is a "new" wavefunction

The idea seems to be that if $x_2 - x_1$ is a tiny interval dx , then it contains energy: E_{AA} where $F(x) = \text{wavefunction} = A$ at $x=0$. ((5)) shows that there is not just energy within $dx = x_2 - x_1$, but also in the regions outside. In fact, $F(x) = A \exp(kx)$ $x < 0$ ($x_0 = 0$) and $A \exp(-kx)$ $x > 0$. This leads to a total energy of:

$$AA \left(-\frac{1}{2m} \right) 2k + AASb = E \quad ((6))$$

The first term represents "kinetic" energy outside of dx , and because dx is tiny, $-\frac{1}{2m} W \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ within dx is replaced with $bS F(0)F(0) = bSAA$. Thus, $F(x)$ is not the real wavefunction, but an approximation. The real wavefunction $W(x)$ behaviour occurs within $dx = x_2 - x_1$, but this region is considered too small and one simply uses the overall result within dx . In other words, one does not follow the changes in the real wavefunction $W(x)$ within $x_2 - x_1$, one just utilizes the classical energy and then multiplies by AA from $F(x)F(x)$.

((5)) is a standard delta function problem with the solution (3):

$$E_{\text{ground}} = -\frac{m}{2} (Sb)(Sb) \quad ((7))$$

If one utilizes the values of A and k from the standard delta function solution, one may see that ((6)) is equivalent to ((7)).

In ((7)) b is unknown and (x_1, x_2) are the classical turning points, which are themselves functions of E_{ground} . Combining ((7)) with ((1)), one obtains:

$$E_{\text{ground}} = -\frac{2}{m} \left(\frac{1}{[(x_2-x_1)(x_2-x_1)]} \right) \quad ((8))$$

This is still a mixed equation because $x_2(E)$ and $x_1(E)$, but it is solvable.

One may verify that E_{ground} yields the exact solution for the oscillator, but not for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls (as already shown in (1) and (2)).

Link to the Uncertainty Principle

In the argument of the previous section, the delta function was introduced by considering x_2-x_1 to be equivalent to dx . Thus, the length scale is broken into tiny units of x_2-x_1 or, in other words, there is an uncertainty in x of x_2-x_1 . This approach seems to use ideas of scaling. In general, Δx in Heisenberg's uncertainty principle $\Delta p \Delta x \leq \hbar/2$ is based on a variance. For Δx , the variance corresponds to a length. For example, for a Gaussian, the ground state of a quantum oscillator, this length is well-known. The approach of the delta function potential seems to be to use $d(x_2-x_1)$ where d is a constant, as a variance. Then, for the equality in the Heisenberg uncertainty principle (which is satisfied for the ground state oscillator):

$$E = (\Delta p) (\Delta p) / 2m = -\frac{1}{2}m \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) \frac{1}{(x_2-x_1)} \frac{1}{(x_2-x_1)} \quad \text{or}$$

$$\Delta x = (x_2-x_1)/2 \quad ((9))$$

In some cases, one sees the uncertainty principle $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar$ in which case $\Delta x = (x_2-x_1)$.

Thus, the process of mapping to a quantum potential $V(x)$ to a delta function with a weight bS and x_2-x_1 being treated as dx seems to be equivalent to the uncertainty principle with x_2-x_1 being Δx or $(x_2-x_1)/2$ being Δx .

Excited States

The approach of (1,2) is extended to excited states. In general, a delta function potential has one energy state, but (1,2) considers excited solutions of the form $F(x) \exp(i G(x))$ and obtains three equations for excited energy levels. For the oscillator, however, there is only one equation $E = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$. The three excited energy equations only approximate the actual result and so we do not pursue excited states here.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine the idea of mapping a quantum potential $V(x)$ into a delta function potential presented in (1). We argue this approach is equivalent to scaling. In other words, the unit of length dx becomes $x_2 - x_1$ where x_1 and x_2 are classical turning points $V(x_i) = E_{\text{ground}}$. Then, one may consider a delta function potential as containing the energy within dx i.e. $bS = b \int_{x_1, x_2} V(x) dx = E(x_2 - x_1)$ where b is an unknown constant. The "mapped" wavefunction $F(x)$ is constant within dx so one may solve the problem: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} F + bS \delta(x - x_0) F = E_{\text{ground}} F$ and combine it with $bS = E_{\text{ground}} (x_2 - x_1)$ so solve for E_{ground} . One may note that $x_2(E)$ and $x_1(E)$. Furthermore, we argue that the result: $E_{\text{ground}} = -\frac{2}{m} \frac{1}{\{ (x_2 - x_1)(x_2 - x_1) \}}$ is of the form of an uncertainty principle result as one has uncertainty in distance the order of $x_2 - x_1$ or officially $(x_2 - x_1)/2$ if one uses $dx dp \geq \hbar/2$ and $E_{\text{ground}} = dp^2 / 2m$. It should be noted that the approach of (1,2) is approximate.

References

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